

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.2779 Max: 63.6316	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1309 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropropic		
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1373-1374	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:		
DEFINITION eastern wall of room 6 (cont. of 1185)				Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction		FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition					
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL/MATRIX			
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
				Compaction		Color	
				<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)							
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:				Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1016, 1273				Covers:			
Is cut by:				Cuts:			
Is filled by:				Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS							
hot dry conditions, excavated with shovel + pickaxe, wall was severely affected by ancient robbing activities + erosion							
DESCRIPTION							
Position within sector: situated at the eastern edge of excavations in 2010, area B							
Shape: linear							
For layers complete this section:							
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):							
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)							
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):							
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight				See rev.			
Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping							
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular							
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded							
Observations:							

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

(reconstruction) lengths: 4,40m width: 0,50m height: 0,40m (state of preserv.)

Description: The wall is badly preserved, but its traces can be followed. Interestingly it has the best preserved ashlar in the hole structure. This block shows still it's original height (0,87m) and orig. width (0,50m), so that the original wall could be reconstructed to a certain extent.

INTERPRETATION

eastern retaining wall of room 6, offset in terms of alignment from wall 1185, therefore it could present a later addition. Please see also SU sheet 1308 for further explanation.

SOIL SAMPLING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):	NON SOIL SAMPLES: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.): Size:	SIEVING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):
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STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Filled-out by <u>CHM</u>	on <u>04.08.2010</u>
	Revised by <u>CHM, AMB</u>	on <u>04.08.2010, 13.07.2011</u>
	PDFd by <u>AMS</u>	on <u>21/7/11</u>
	Entered by	on